

A Study of the Conductivity of Solutions of Zinc oxide in Caustic Soda Solution.

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A study of the conductivity of solutions of alumina in caustic soda solution by Mata Prasad, Mehta, and Joshi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 973) has suggested the existence in these solutions of sodium aluminate complexes with a lower ratio of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{Na}_2\text{O}$ than any of the well established sodium aluminates. In the present work an attempt has been made to see whether similar evidence is forthcoming in the case of solutions of zinc oxide in caustic soda solutions.

The literature dealing with the study of the constitution of solutions of zinc oxide in sodium hydroxide can be conveniently classified under three headings:—

- (a) Study of the phase rule equilibria (solubility etc.),
- (b) Study of hydrogen Ion concentration by *e.m.f.* measurement.
- (c) Study of conductivity.

(a) The greater part of the published work on solutions of ZnO in NaOH solution falls under this head. A large variety of solid phases have been reported, and much of the disagreement in the results of the different workers is no doubt due to indeterminacy of the solid phase. The most important references are those of Muller and Fauvel (*Z. Elektro Chem.*, 1924, 33, 140), Fricke (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 136, 321, 344) and Goudriaan (*Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1920, 39, 505). Other references are Robenbauer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 30, 331), Klein (*ibid.*, 1912, 74, 167), Gutbier (*ibid.*, 1924, 176, 363), Dietrich and Johnston (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 1419) and Forster and Gunther (*Z. Elektro Chem.*, 1899, 6, 301), (b) Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2120) used the hydrogen electrode to follow the changes in p_{H} during the titration of Zn^{++} solutions with alkali. He found no inflections in the curve corresponding either to NaHZnO_2 (here contradicting Hildebrand's earlier work—*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 785) or to Na_2ZnO_2 .

(c) Certain conductivity measurements were made by Hantzsch (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 30, 289) in order to ascertain the existence of colloidal $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ in zincate solutions. He concluded that the colloidal form is present to a great extent, but he is ruthlessly criticised by Klein (*loc. cit.*). Certain *e.m.f.* measurements done

in 1927 by Dietrich also indicate that practically all the zincate in the solution is in the ionic form. Dietz, Dans and Tower (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 605) however succeeded in preparing colloidal solutions of $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$.

This survey indicates that the only complexes for which there is any considerable amount of evidence are those in which the ratio $\text{ZnO}:\text{Na}_2\text{O}$ is either 2:1 or 1:1 ($n=2$ or $n=1$). But since in the case of the aluminates Mata Prasad (*loc. cit.*) found discontinuities in the ratio-conductivity curves at the values 2:3, 1:2, 2:5, 1:3, 1:4, for the ratio $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:\text{Na}_2\text{O}$, it seemed worth while to examine the ratio-conductivity curves in the case of ZnO for similar evidence, although it is not possible to prepare solutions of ZnO in NaOH solutions having a value for 'n' of even as high as 0.5.

In the present work therefore an attempt has been made to gain information regarding the existence of complexes in strongly alkaline solutions by following the method used by Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1155) for sodium silicate, and by Mata Prasad for sodium aluminate. Their method consisted in obtaining the conductivity ratio (ratio of SiO_2 or Al_2O_3 to Na_2O) curve. But the points on this curve were not obtained directly but indirectly from the measured conductivity-dilution curves at various ratios. This indirectness of their method has serious disadvantages in such strongly alkaline solutions in which impurities are very difficult to avoid. In the present work therefore the conductivity-ratio curves are directly determined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the present experiments the strongest solution of ZnO in NaOH solution obtainable was placed in the conductivity cell, and a solution of NaOH of the same normality (with respect to NaOH) was added from a burette, the change of conductivity being measured meanwhile. The solution being very concentrated and the conductivity therefore high, a special form of cell was designed and made. This is shown in Fig. 1. The electrodes are formed by platinum wires fused through the ends of the glass tubes FF' (Fig. 1), ground flush with the glass and then covered with platinum black in the usual way. These tubes are supported rigidly by the wooden block B which is screwed down to a collar A, clamped round the neck of the flask in such a way that the position of the electrodes in the flask is rigidly determined. With a cell of this design the correction

of the cell constant for the variation in the volume of liquid in the flask was reduced to very small dimensions. The resistance of the solutions was measured in the ordinary way with a Wheatstone bridge circuit, using a buzzer and telephones. The estimated accuracy of the measurement of conductivity is about $\pm 1\%$.

The analyses of the solutions gave some difficulty at first. It was found, however, that the NaOH can be accurately titrated in presence of ZnO by using the indicator Brilliant Cresyl Blue. This method would not be applicable in dilute solutions. The ZnO in solution was determined by titration with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution, using diphenylamine as an indicator (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 356). This titration was found extremely satisfactory. The cell flask was of Monax glass, but all other glass vessels used in making up the solutions were of Kavalier glass since this contains a larger proportion of alkaline oxides, and may therefore be expected to be more resistant to the strongly alkaline solutions used. Kavalier glass has also the advantage of being free from Zn and Al.

The NaOH used was Merck's pure sticks. These were dissolved in about an equal weight of water, keeping the solution cool, to give a solution of about 16N. This was then allowed to stand

Fig. 1.

- A Annular split collar with cork washer clamped rigidly by means of two screws (not shown) round the neck of the 160 c.c. Monax Flask E.
- B. Wooden block carrying electrode tubes FF' and terminals (not shown) to which the lead wires GG' are connected. There is also a third hole (not shown) through the block by which the nozzle of the burette is introduced.
- CD and C'D'. Brass bolts and nuts by means of which B can be screwed firmly down onto A.
- HH', Platinum wires, fused through the ends of the tubes FF', ground flush with the glass, and blacked with platinum.

for several days, until all solid matter (Na_2CO_3 etc.) had settled. It was then carefully siphoned off and diluted for use as required. This procedure avoids the highly undesirable filtration through glass-wool. The ZnO used was Merck's 'Pure', which analysis showed to be 99.5% ZnO. It was found necessary to boil the ZnO with the NaOH solution in order to get it to dissolve. With 14 N alkali, indicated by Muller's curves as the best to use, the maximum ratio of ZnO: Na_2O obtainable was found to be about 0.400. This solution was allowed to settle and the clear liquid diluted for use as required. A check made with alkali only, boiling for a similar length of time and under similar conditions showed no appreciable change of conductivity due to the heating.

In each experiment 50 C.c. of the ZnO solution were placed in the cell and the conductivity measured. Alkali of the same normality (as calculated from the titration with 1.0N acid with Brilliant Cresyl Blue as Indicator) was then added from a burette, and the conductivity determined at intervals. If 'v' was the volume added, and n_0 the initial ZnO: Na_2O ratio as determined by analysis, n_v was calculated from the formula: $-n_v = n_0 \times (50/50 + v)$. Check analyses at the end of each experiment showed that this method of calculation (neglecting possible volume changes) was satisfactory. Particularly in the more concentrated, and therefore more viscous, solutions, time had to be allowed for equilibrium to be reached, but if the solution was frequently shaken, 30-40 minutes were found to be sufficient for this. The ZnO solutions were kept for at least a week after being made up before they were used. All experiments were carried out in an electrically regulated thermostat at 25.0° with a maximum temperature variation of $\pm 0.03^\circ$.

At the beginning and end of each experiment the electrodes were transferred to KCl solution to verify that no change had taken place in the cell-constant, due to action of the solution on the electrodes. The cell-constant was determined with 0.1N KCl solution.

Results.

The results are given in Table I, and plotted in Fig. 2. 'n' is the ratio of mols. ZnO to mols. Na_2O ; λ is the equivalent conductivity with respect to normality of NaOH, calculated from $\lambda = \frac{10^3 \cdot K}{NR}$ where K is the cell-constant; R the observed resistance, and N the

normality with respect to NaOH. The curves are nearly linear, but show a slight concavity towards the 'n' axis. There is, however, no evidence of any discontinuities in any of them over the range covered. The four points from Experiment B, which are shown in Fig. 2 in brackets, are of some interest in connection with the time lag. In determining all other points in Experiment B, a time of not less than 40 minutes was allowed to elapse after addition of the alkali. But in the case of the four points mentioned, the time intervals were only 15, 15, 7, 7, minutes respectively.

Fig. 2.

TABLE I.
Temp. 25°.

Normality of NaOH=11·7		Normality of NaOH=8·7.					
Exp. A. NaOH—11·7N.		Exp. B. NaOH—8·7 N		Exp. C. NaOH—6·0N		Exp. D. NaOH—4·1N	
κ	λ	κ	λ	κ	λ	κ	λ
0·864	7·69	0·382	17·6	0·380	36·7	0·380	58·9
0·351	7·72	0·367	18·0	0·359	37·4	0·364	69·9
0·339	7·96	0·347	18·7	0·341	38·3	0·336	61·3
0·322	8·44	0·324	19·5	0·312	39·7	0·295	63·6
0·303	8·80	0·303	20·1	0·283	41·3	0·262	66·1
0·272	9·48	0·281	20·6	0·255	42·8	0·234	67·8
0·242	10·29	0·262	21·2	0·227	44·5	0·196	71·00
0·212	10·98	0·242	21·7	0·200	46·3	0·164	74·2
0·183	11·67	0·222	22·5	0·186	47·5	0·147	75·7
0·160	12·60	0·222	23·4	0·169	48·6	0·000	89·6
0·000	16·96	0·204	24·2	0·150	49·8		
		0·185	25·2				
		0·159	25·9				
		0·139	27·0				
		0·000	33·7				

A similar set of experiments done at 30°, with less satisfactorily regulated experimental conditions, using solutions from 2·5 to 11·0N, also showed no sign of any discontinuity.

The curves thus show no indication of any complexes, with a value for ' κ ' of less than 0·4, formed in the solutions.

The ratio of the equivalent conductivity of the solution containing the ratio 1:3 ($\kappa=0·333$) to the equivalent conductivity of the NaOH solution of corresponding normality, varies from about 45% to 75% in the solutions dealt with, being smaller in the more concentrated solutions. Comparing this with Mata Prasad's curves it will be seen that the slope in the present case is considerably less.

Additional Note.

A single experiment has also been carried out with the apparatus described above on a solution of alumina on sodium hydroxide solution. The alumina content of the solution is subject to slight uncertainty but the part of the ratio-conductivity curve covered is roughly that from $n=0.400$ to $n=0.220$ (n =ratio-mols. Al_2O_3 /mols. Na_2O). The discontinuities found by Mata Prasad (*loc. cit.* p. 979) in this curve at the ratios 1:3 and 1:4 are certainly well taken in by the present experiment. The normality of the solution with respect to NaOH is 1.44. The 9 points determined approximate closely to a straight line. There is, in particular, no sign whatever of the very remarkable reversal of direction found by Mata Prasad at the ratio 1:3. It is hoped that it may be possible to extend these experiments on alumina solutions. The author wishes to acknowledge his debt to Mr. S. C. Banerjee for assistance in the analysis of this solution.

Summary.

The conductivity of solutions of Zinc Oxide in Sodium Hydroxide solutions is examined at various dilutions with the ratio mols. ZnO /mols. Na_2O varying from 1:2.5 to 1:7. The curves for ratio-conductivity are found to show no discontinuities which might indicate the existence of complexes in the solution.

A brief survey is given of previous work on solutions of zinc oxide in caustic soda solution.

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